

Cesium uptake studies on synthetic $[\text{KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{OH}_2]$ gel and ordinary portland cement admixture

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Cesium uptake studies have been carried out on synthetic hydrogel having composition of mineral phlogopite and ordinary portland cement (OPC) admixture at room temperature. Selectivity of the gel-OPC admixture for Cs^+ has been examined in presence of 1000 times concentrated solution of competing cations : Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and Ca^{2+} . The gel-OPC admixture exhibits good Cs retention capacity while OPC alone holds negligible amount of cesium. The Cs^+ ion is less hydrated and can easily access the exchange site in the initial stages of exchange, however the framework of exchanger needs to be expanded to accommodate more amount of Cs^+ . Cesium uptake studies were performed in presence of high concentration of Na^+ and in pure cesium solutions. The data shows that 10.82 meq of cesium per 100 g of the gel is picked up at room temperature.

Fluorine micas have assumed importance in the literature of crystal chemistry as many of these substances are now commercial products¹. Synthetic potassium magnesium aluminosilicate hydrogel is close in composition to phlogopite mineral $[\text{KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{OH}_2]$ having Si : Al ratio 3 : 1. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) is commonly used as the solidifying material for aqueous and solid low level radioactive waste but immobilization of cesium in the ordinary portland cement is difficult because of high leach rates of cesium in alkaline medium admixture². Additives such as aluminosilicate hydrogel can increase the retention capacity of the OPC. Thus aluminosilicate hydrogel gel containing OPC admixture could be used for immobilization of cesium from nuclear effluents generated from nuclear power plants³. This communication reports data on cesium sorption onto hydrothermally synthesized aluminosilicate hydrogel gel when it is added in ordinary portland cement as an additive.

Results and discussion

The elemental analyses for K, Mg, Al and Si suggest that the hydrothermal product is close in composition of $[\text{KMg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{OH}_2]$. The analytical values of Mg, K, Al and Si are in good agreement with the calculated values. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of the sample shows the maxima at 16.86 Å ($2\theta = 5.23$). The other prominent peaks are observed at $D = 9.26$ and 1.53 Å. The X-ray powder diffraction pattern resembles that of disordered potassium fluorophlogopite which may gradually be ordered to 1M type.

The ordering of phase begins at 425°, below which the mineral exists in a gel like structure. The synthetic product is more likely 1M than 3T type⁴. The selective uptake of cesium may be attributed to the different ways of shifting the cation layer relative to the Si_2O_5 network⁵. The EDS⁶ analysis of Cs^+ loaded gel shows that Si : Al ratio remains unchanged, i.e. 3 : 1, indicating that the Cs^+ occupies the sites of the compensating cations in the hydrogel which in this case are Mg^{2+} and K^+ . Table 1 shows the selective sorption of cesium from mixed cationic solution in presence of

Table 1. Selective sorption of Cs^+ onto 1 : 3 admixture of aluminosilicate hydrogel + OPC in presence of competing cations*

Normality of soln. = 0.0005 N Cs^+ + 0.1 N M^{n+} , where $\text{M}^{n+} = \text{Na}^+$, K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , wt. of exch. = 25 mg, vol. of soln. = 25 ml, equilibrium time = 72 h, wt. of OPC = 75 mg

Ion pair (Cs + M^{n+})	Initial Cs^+ $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Final Cs^+ $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Δ	K_d ml g^{-1}	% Cs removal
Cs + Na	12.4	5.8	6.6	1138	53.22
Cs + K	12.4	9.0	3.4	378	27.41
Cs + Mg	6.4	2.8	3.6	1286	56.25
Cs + Ca	16.0	5.8	10.2	1759	63.75
Cs + Ba	6.0	5.0	1.0	200	16.66
Cs + Sr	20.0	13.8	6.2	449	31.00

* Δ = Initial Cs^+ concn. – final concn.; K_d = distribution coefficient = $(C_o/C_e) \times A/M$; C_o = initial concn. of Cs^+ ; C_e = final concn. of Cs^+ ; A = vol. of soln. (ml); M = mass of the exchanger in (g); % Cs removal = $\Delta \times 100/\text{initial Cs concn.}$

ordinary portland cement (OPC). The data show that 53.22 % of Cs⁺ is removed when aluminosilicate hydrogel and OPC are in 1 : 3 ratio in the admixture. The selectivity study reveals that K⁺ and Ba²⁺ ions are most competing in presence of which K_d values are found to be approximately 378 and 200 ml g⁻¹, respectively, and this is due to large cationic radii of these hydrated ions. The gel exhibits high selectivity (K_d = 1138 ml g⁻¹) for Cs⁺ in the presence of excess of Na⁺ ions indicating its potential for application in solidification and immobilization of alkaline radioactive waste which contains very high concentration of sodium⁷. Table 2 shows the sorption of Cs⁺ on aluminosilicate

Table 2. Selective uptake of Cs⁺ onto potassium aluminosilicate hydrogel gel in presence of competing Na⁺ cation*

Normality of Na	Initial Cs ⁺ μg ml ⁻¹	Final Cs ⁺ μg ml ⁻¹	Δ	Moles of Cs	K _d ml g ⁻¹	%Cs removal
Volume of solution = 5 ml :						
0.2	12.5	5.3	7.2	5.41 × 10 ⁻⁵	271.69	57.60
0.4	12.0	5.8	6.2	4.66 × 10 ⁻⁵	213.79	51.66
0.6	11.2	5.8	5.4	4.06 × 10 ⁻⁵	186.20	48.21
0.8	10.2	5.4	4.8	3.60 × 10 ⁻⁵	177.77	47.05
1.0	10.5	6.7	3.8	2.85 × 10 ⁻⁵	113.43	36.19
1.2	9.5	6.1	3.4	2.55 × 10 ⁻⁵	111.47	35.78
1.4	8.0	4.8	3.2	2.40 × 10 ⁻⁵	133.30	40.00
1.6	10.0	7.0	3.0	2.25 × 10 ⁻⁵	85.71	30.00
1.8	9.5	7.7	1.8	1.35 × 10 ⁻⁵	46.75	18.94
2.0	9.5	8.1	1.4	1.05 × 10 ⁻⁵	34.56	14.73
Volume of solution = 25 ml :						
0.2	16.0	10.2	5.8	4.36 × 10 ⁻⁵	568.62	36.25
0.4	16.2	11.2	5.0	3.75 × 10 ⁻⁵	446.42	30.86
0.6	12.8	9.0	3.8	2.85 × 10 ⁻⁵	422.22	29.68
0.8	12.6	9.8	2.8	2.10 × 10 ⁻⁵	285.71	22.22
1.0	10.4	8.2	2.2	1.65 × 10 ⁻⁵	268.29	21.15
1.2	10.0	8.4	1.6	1.20 × 10 ⁻⁵	90.47	16.00
1.4	8.0	6.9	1.1	8.27 × 10 ⁻⁶	159.42	13.75
1.6	7.6	6.8	0.8	6.01 × 10 ⁻⁶	117.64	10.52
1.8	6.4	5.8	0.6	4.51 × 10 ⁻⁶	103.44	9.37
2.0	7.6	7.4	0.2	1.50 × 10 ⁻⁶	27.02	2.63

*Normality of soln. = 0.0001 N Cs⁺ + 0.2 to 2 N Na⁺; equilibrium time = 24 h.

Wt. of exchanger = 25 mg.

hydrogel gel in presence of increasing concentration of Na⁺ from 0.2 to 2.0 N. The data reveal that Cs⁺ uptake decreases from 57.66 to 14.73% as concentration of Na⁺ increases from 0.2 to 2.0 N. The comparative volume study of % Cs removal shows that with increase in volume of eluent from 5 to 25 ml the Cs⁺ uptake decreases from 57.60 to 36.25%,

respectively, for 0.2 N Na⁺. The K_d value decreases linearly from 271.69 to 34.56 for 5 ml of eluent and it also decreases from 568.62 to 27.02 ml g⁻¹ for 25 ml of eluent. Fig. 1 indicates that with increase in Na⁺ concentration the moles

Fig. 1. Moles of Cs on synthetic aluminosilicate hydrogel in presence of Na cation as function of volume.

of cesium sorbed by the gel decreases from 5.41 × 10⁻⁵ to 1.05 × 10⁻⁵ for 5 ml of eluent and from 4.36 × 10⁻⁵ to 1.50 × 10⁻⁶ for 25 ml of eluent. Table 3 shows the sorption data of Cs⁺ in pure cesium solution from 100 to 1000 mg dm⁻³. The maximum uptake is 10.82 meq of cesium per 100 g of the gel. The hydrogel gives a pH ≈ 8.80 in water which is compatible with the pH of ordinary portland cement which releases additional Ca(OH)₂ in the admixture. The hydration of cement is accompanied by the formation of complex hydrated silicate phases and C-S-H gel, therefore, interaction of the hydrogel with such phases remains unpredictable. Thus, the gel could be effectively used for immobilization of cesium from mixed cationic solutions. The Cs⁺ ion (effective ionic radii 1.67 Å) is less hydrated and can easily access the exchange site in the initial stages of exchange, however, the framework of exchanger needs to be expanded to accommodate more amount of Cs⁺ which requires much energy and flexible hydrated ion⁸. It may be concluded that the gel when used as an additive to ordinary portland cement could be useful for separation and fixation of cesium from rad-waste effluent.

Table 3. Cesium uptake data on synthetic potassium aluminosilicate hydrogel gel

Wt. of exchanger = 25 mg, vol. of soln. = 10 ml, equilibration time = 24 h

Initial Cs ⁺ μg ml ⁻¹	Final Cs ⁺ μg ml ⁻¹	Δ	% Cs removal	K _d ml g ⁻¹	Meq/100 g
120	50	70	58.33	560.00	2.10
200	90	110	55.00	488.88	3.30
300	160	140	46.66	350.00	4.21
390	230	160	41.02	278.26	4.81
490	270	220	44.89	325.92	6.61
580	340	240	41.37	282.35	7.21
650	385	265	40.76	275.32	7.96
770	470	300	38.96	255.31	9.02
900	580	320	35.55	220.68	9.62
1100	740	360	32.72	194.59	10.82

Experimental

The aluminosilicate hydrogel was synthesized as follows: metal ions K, Mg, Si, Al along with OH ions were taken in molar ratios 1 : 3 : 3 : 1 : 2, respectively, to give a homogeneous paste in double-distilled decarbonated water (10 ml). Aqueous solutions of Mg(NO₃)₂, K₂SiO₃ and KOH in stoichiometric ratios were used as starting materials. On mixing the aqueous solutions a white glassy mass separated out. The thick precipitate after thorough homogenization was then transformed to a teflon-lined stainless steel pressure vessel⁹. Additional amount of water was added to keep total solid-water ratio to 1 : 5. The mixture was autoclaved in teflon-lined stainless steel pressure vessel under saturated steam pressure and kept in an oven maintained at 180° for 72 h. After hydrothermal treatment, the contents were filtered, washed with distilled water and dried in an oven at 120°. The chemical composition of the product was verified by elemental analysis using atomic absorption/flame emission spectroscopy following borate fusion method for silicate materials¹⁰. X-Ray pattern of the gel was recorded on a computer interfaced PW-1820 diffractometer system using Ni filtered CuK_α radiations.

The gel (25 mg) was equilibrated with mixed cationic solution (25 ml) containing 0.0001 N Cs⁺ and 0.1 M each

of the competing cations, viz. Na⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺ and Ca²⁺ separately. Sorption studies were carried out in presence of 0.2–2 N Na⁺ changing the volume of cationic solution from 10 to 25 ml. Cesium uptake study was performed separately on pure cesium solution ranging from 100 to 1000 ml dm⁻³. Cesium was analyzed by GBC 902 double beam atomic absorption spectrophotometer at wavelengths 852.1 nm. All experiments were performed in duplicate. Other experimental conditions are shown in Tables 1–3.

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